

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D9.6 Standardisation assessment report - Interim

SPINMATE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101069712.

Document details

Project Information	
Project Acronym/ Name:	SPINMATE
Project URL:	www.spinmate.eu
Project Type:	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
EU CALL:	HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-05 (Manufacturing technology development for solid-state batteries (SSB, Generations 4a - 4b batteries) (Batteries Partnership))
Grant Agreement No.:	101069712
Project Start Date:	01/08/2022
Project End Date:	31/07/2026
Document details	
Work package:	WP9 - Communication, dissemination, and exploitation
Deliverable:	D9.6 - Standardisation assessment report - Interim
Due date of Deliverable:	31/01/2025
Actual Submission Date:	31/01/2025
Name of Lead Beneficiary for this deliverable:	Marco Duarte (INOVA)
Reviewed by:	Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha (AVESTA), Ana Rita Araújo (INEGI), Leif Olav Jøsang (CERPOTECH)
Revision:	23/01/2025
Dissemination Level:	PU

Document History			
Version	Date	Comment	Modifications made by
0.1	01.10.2024	Standardisation SubTask Planning	Marco Duarte, Catarina Carneiro, Hugo Faria (INOVA)
0.2	21.10.2024	Deliverable structure and methodology	Marco Duarte (INOVA)
0.3	28.10.2024	Revision of Standardisation plan	Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha (AVESTA)
0.4	04.11.2024	Standardisation Assessment Survey	Marco Duarte (INOVA)
0.5	10.01.2025	Gathering of standardisation contributes	Marco Duarte, Mafalda Santos (INOVA)
1.0	22.01.2025	First draft	Marco Duarte (INOVA)
1.0	23.01.2025	Content review, add more abbreviations to the list, and minor revisions	Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha (AVESTA)
1.1	27.01.2025	Proofreading and minor revisions	Leif Olav Jøsang (CERPOTECH)
1.2	27.01.2025	Content review and minor suggestions	Ana Rita Araújo (INEGI)
1.3	29.01.2025	Final Review	Marco Duarte, Tânia Moreira (INOVA)
2.0	31.01.2025	Finalisation and submission	Rahmandhika Firdauzha Hary Hernandha (AVESTA)

Disclaimer

Any dissemination of results reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Copyright message

© Partners of the SPINMATE Consortium, 2021
 This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Glossary and Abbreviations	
CAM	Cathode Active Material
CE	Conformité Européenne
EC	European Commission
EoL	End of Life
EPR	Extended Producer Responsibility
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicle
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practice
HMI	Human-Machine Interface
IEC	Standard code from the International Electrotechnical Commission
ISO	Standard code from the International Organization for Standardization
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LiBs	Lithium-ion Batteries
LMT	Light means of transport
NMC	Lithium nickel manganese cobalt oxides
PLC	Programmable Logic Controllers
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEI	Solid Electrolyte Interphase
SOP	Standard Operational Procedure
SPE	Solid Polymer Electrolyte
SSB	Solid-State Battery
SSE	Solid-State Electrolyte
SoA	State of the Art
SoH	State of Health
UN	United Nations

Contents

Executive Summary.....	7
1. Introduction	8
2. Batteries Applicability Priorities and EU Battery Requirements	10
3. Standards in SPINMATE	13
4. Standardisation Methodology	14
5. Standardisation First Results – Part I	18
5.1 Cell Assembly.....	18
Cathode Preparation	18
Anode Preparation	19
Electrolyte Membrane Preparation	19
10 Ah Cell Assembly	19
5.2 Separator Membrane Manufacturing	20
5.3 Sustainable SSB Cells, Modules, and Packs.....	21
Eco-Design and Disassembly	21
Guidelines for Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design	22
5.4 SPINMATE Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design.....	22
6. Standardisation First Results – Part II	26
6.1 Sustainability.....	26
6.2 Performance.....	28
6.3 Safety.....	29
6.4 Collection	30
6.5 Recycling and Second Life.....	31
6.6 Content and Labelling	31
6.7 Communication	33
6.8 Management	33
6.9 New EU Battery Regulation updates	34
7. Standardisation First Results – Part III	37
7.1 Use Case #1 – TUBS: Adhesive strength measurement	37
7.2 Use Case #2 – CID: Cathode preparation by wet processing.....	38
7.3 Use Case #3 – INEGI: Life cycle assessment of partners activities	39
8. Conclusions	40
ANNEX 1 – Standardisation Survey	41

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Standardisation Activities roadmap in SPINMATE.....	14
Figure 2 - Standardisation evaluation methodology in SPINMATE	15
Figure 3 - Radar Chart	17
Figure 4 - SPINMATE Radar Chart	25

Executive Summary

Standardisation plays a pivotal role in the SPINMATE project, ensuring the development of solid-state battery cells that meet stringent requirements in the electric vehicle sector while aligning with international and EU regulations. By prioritizing sustainability throughout the battery lifecycle—from eco-design and production to recycling and second-life applications—the project supports the European Green Deal and advances the EU’s goals for a circular economy, resource efficiency, and climate neutrality. SPINMATE employs advanced methodologies, such as digital twins and machine learning, to optimize production processes across key manufacturing stages, including cathode and anode preparation, solid electrolyte membrane production, and cell assembly. Collaborative efforts with initiatives like SOLID4B and active engagement with standardisation committees have enabled SPINMATE to contribute to future standards development while aligning its technologies with evolving regulations. The project’s standardisation activities are guided by a two-stage evaluation methodology that assesses current standards, identifies gaps, and proposes advancements to align with market needs and sustainability goals. Tools like the Radar Chart and Standardisation Assessment Survey ensure effective tracking of standardisation maturity and application, providing insights for compliance and industry-wide adoption. With its focus on sustainability, performance, and safety, SPINMATE not only enhances customer satisfaction and competitive positioning but also contributes to the EU’s vision of a sustainable and innovative battery industry that supports the global transition to clean energy.

1. Introduction

A standard is defined as “a document, established by a consensus of subject matter experts and approved by a recognized body, that provides guidance on the design, use, or performance of materials, products, processes, services, systems, or individuals”. According to the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), standards “provide, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines, or characteristics for activities or their results, aimed at achieving the optimum degree of order in a given context.”¹.

The concept of standards management arises from the need to address the complexity and large volume of information that must be processed collaboratively by a group of individuals. People inherently represent a dynamic element within any project or organization, bringing diverse cultures, experiences, and approaches that can influence outcomes, even when following the same methodologies. In this context, having clearly defined written procedures becomes not only essential but also a strategic advantage. These procedures capture and consolidate accumulated knowledge and experiences, transforming them into structured forms, records, and written guidelines or policies that enhance consistency and efficiency.

ISO is one of the world’s leading developers and publishers of international standards for business, government, and communities. Among its standards, ISO 9000² —a comprehensive set of international standards for quality management and quality assurance—stands out as the most widely adopted and implemented. Initially designed to help companies effectively document the elements of a quality management system to maintain operational efficiency, ISO 9000 has evolved into a vital tool for enhancing marketing efforts and competitiveness in the global market.

In the early years, customers were satisfied with standardised products, low costs, and just-in-time (JIT) manufacturing. However, this model was later replaced by a preference for customised products, which came with longer lead times and higher costs. Today, this landscape has shifted once again. Competing organisations are adopting mixed-model production to deliver customised products with shorter lead times and lower costs. Intense market competition, evolving customer demands, and advancements in machinery have transformed the paradigm, placing customer satisfaction and competitive positioning at the forefront. In recent production scenarios, industries are striving to move from mass production to mass customisation, tailoring goods to customer preferences, as standardised products with short lead times no longer meet market expectations.

Standardisation is crucial for advancing the electric vehicle (EV) market, particularly in battery development and production. It ensures safety, efficiency, and sustainability by providing consistent guidelines for manufacturing, testing, and recycling processes. Standardisation also supports the shift from mass production to customisation, aligning with evolving customer demands and competitive market dynamics. In the EU, these efforts are aligned with the European Commission’s push for harmonised standards to drive innovation, interoperability, and the transition to sustainable mobility solutions.

On December 9, 2022, the European Commission welcomed a provisional political agreement between the European Parliament and the Council aimed at making all batteries placed on the EU market more sustainable, circular, and safe³. This agreement builds upon the Commission’s proposal from December 2020 and addresses social, economic, and environmental aspects

¹ ISO - [Consumers and Standards: Partnership for a Better World](#)

² ISO - [Quality Management](#)

³ EC Press Release – [Green Deal: EU agrees new law on more sustainable and circular batteries to support EU’s energy transition and competitive industry](#)

related to all types of batteries. The new law introduces sustainability requirements on carbon footprint, recycled content, performance, and durability, to be implemented gradually from 2024 onwards. It also establishes a comprehensive regulatory framework on Extended Producer Responsibility, set to apply by mid-2025, with progressively higher collection targets. For portable batteries, the targets are 63% by 2027 and 73% by 2030, while for batteries from light means of transport, the targets are 51% by 2028 and 61% by 2031. All collected batteries must be recycled, achieving high levels of recovery, particularly for valuable materials such as copper, cobalt, lithium, nickel, and lead. Companies placing batteries on the EU market will need to demonstrate that the materials used in their manufacturing are sourced responsibly, identifying and mitigating social and environmental risks associated with the extraction, processing, and trading of raw materials.

This regulatory framework aligns with the European Green Deal's objectives, promoting a circular economy and zero pollution by ensuring batteries are sustainable throughout their entire lifecycle—from material sourcing to collection, recycling, and repurposing. In the current energy context, these rules establish an essential framework to foster the development of a competitive and sustainable battery industry, supporting Europe's clean energy transition and reducing dependence on fuel imports. Batteries are a key technology that plays a central role in advancing the EU's climate neutrality goals by 2050.

2. Batteries Applicability Priorities and EU Battery Requirements

The use of batteries in the context of clean energy transition is a key priority for Europe, particularly in the automotive sector. To understand better how standardisation can take an important role, it was analysed over the applicability of standards on batteries and respective waste management were analysed to identify which are the key priorities to act over the electrification of the automotive sector & Global GHG emission. These priorities identified will be used as a reference for analysing how SPINMATE will be contributing to such European Commission goals.

SOURCE: REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL concerning batteries and waste batteries, repealing Directive 2006/66/EC and amending Regulation (EU) No 2019/1020⁴.

1. **Sustainability:** The regulation sets the foundation for the European Green Deal by making sustainability the central priority in the entire lifecycle of batteries. It mandates eco-design and efficient use of resources, aiming to reduce the carbon footprint of battery production and promote sustainable sourcing of raw materials. By prioritizing reduced environmental impacts, the regulation aligns with global climate neutrality targets, the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and the EU's commitment to a circular economy. The overarching aim is to position Europe as a leader in green energy solutions, reducing dependency on non-renewable resources while fostering innovation in battery technologies.

2. **Performance:** To support Europe's green transition and enhance consumer trust, the regulation sets ambitious performance standards for batteries. It emphasizes metrics such as capacity, durability, and leakage prevention, aiming to extend battery lifespan and ensure efficient energy use. The focus on rigorous performance testing, including assessments of capacity fade, internal resistance, and energy round-trip efficiency, reflects a commitment to high-quality, reliable products that can meet the growing demand for renewable energy storage. This aligns with the EU's broader goals of improving energy efficiency and fostering technological advancements in the clean energy sector.

3. **Safety:** Safety is a key policy priority, reflecting the need to protect consumers, workers, and the environment from potential risks associated with battery use. The regulation enforces stringent safety requirements throughout the entire lifecycle, from production to disposal, including comprehensive tests for thermal stability and leakage prevention. By ensuring the safe handling of batteries, the regulation supports the EU's vision of a secure and sustainable energy market, mitigating risks such as fires, explosions, and exposure to hazardous chemicals, thus enhancing public confidence and safety across Europe.

4. **Collection:** The regulation establishes ambitious collection targets for waste batteries, demonstrating the EU's commitment to resource efficiency and waste reduction. By setting mandatory collection rates and promoting efficient collection schemes, the policy aims to significantly reduce the environmental footprint of batteries. This approach is aligned with the EU's broader circular economy strategy, ensuring that valuable materials are recovered and reintroduced into the production cycle, minimizing waste and supporting global sustainability goals such as responsible consumption and production (SDG 12).

4

https://ec.europa.eu/environment/pdf/waste/batteries/Proposal_for_a_Regulation_on_batteries_and_waste_batteries.pdf

5. Recycling and Second Life: Maximizing resource efficiency is a central priority for EU policy-makers, highlighted by the regulation's focus on recycling and repurposing batteries. It sets high recycling efficiency targets for various battery chemistries, encouraging the recovery of critical materials and reducing dependency on raw imports. Additionally, the regulation promotes second-life applications, particularly for electric vehicle batteries, which can be repurposed for energy storage systems. This policy approach supports the EU's climate and energy objectives, contributing to a more resilient and circular economy while aligning with the global shift towards sustainable industrial practices.

6. Content (Chemicals) & Labelling: The regulation addresses the EU's priorities for reducing hazardous substances and enhancing consumer information. It introduces strict limits on the use of toxic chemicals in batteries, safeguarding human health and the environment. Comprehensive labelling requirements provide clear information on chemical content, environmental risks, and proper disposal methods, supporting informed consumer choices and responsible market behaviour. This transparency is crucial for aligning with EU sustainability policies and the global push for safer, greener products that meet high environmental standards.

7. Communication: Effective communication and transparency are fundamental pillars of the regulation, ensuring robust information flow between stakeholders, including policy-makers, manufacturers, and consumers. The introduction of a digital product passport reflects the EU's commitment to enhancing traceability, enabling better compliance monitoring, and facilitating informed decision-making. By providing detailed information on origin, performance, and recycling guidelines, the digital passport supports global sustainability goals, helping consumers make eco-conscious choices and enabling efficient resource management across the supply chain.

8. Management of Waste Batteries and Accumulators: The regulation sets a comprehensive framework for the responsible management of waste batteries, aligning with the EU's waste hierarchy principles and the global circular economy agenda. It implements extended producer responsibility (EPR), requiring manufacturers to finance the collection, treatment, and recycling of waste batteries. This policy measure ensures the safe and efficient handling of end-of-life products, minimizes environmental risks, and promotes the recovery of valuable materials, contributing to the EU's goal of achieving zero waste and supporting the transition towards a sustainable, resource-efficient economy.

Under the scope of batteries sector, it is also important to consider and evaluate key updates from **EU Directive 2006/66/EC to the new EU Battery Regulation (Regulation 2023/1542)**, by analysing batteries' requirements for Europe, as well to identify potential gaps which projects and initiatives, such as SPINMATE, can support the achievement of European goals.

- 1. CE Conformity Assessment:** From August 18, 2024, all batteries placed on the EU market must carry the CE marking, indicating conformity with essential safety, performance, and environmental standards set out in the regulation. The CE marking process requires manufacturers to conduct a conformity assessment, verifying that their batteries meet the legal requirements related to safety, chemical composition, and sustainability. This process involves documenting compliance and ensuring traceability, which is crucial for market surveillance and consumer protection within the EU.
- 2. Battery Passport:** The regulation introduces an electronic battery passport, mandatory for industrial batteries, electric vehicle (EV) batteries, and light means of transport (LMT) batteries starting February 18, 2027. This digital passport will contain detailed information about the battery's origin, chemical composition, performance metrics, and

recycling instructions. The aim is to enhance transparency, facilitate traceability, and support the circular economy by enabling efficient end-of-life management and repurposing of batteries. It also empowers consumers and stakeholders to make informed decisions and ensures compliance with EU sustainability standards.

3. **Supply Chain Due Diligence:** Starting August 18, 2025, companies must implement supply chain due diligence policies for batteries containing critical raw materials such as cobalt, natural graphite, lithium, or nickel. The regulation requires manufacturers and importers to assess and mitigate risks associated with human rights abuses, environmental damage, and unethical practices in their supply chains. This due diligence obligation aligns with the EU's broader goals of promoting responsible sourcing and ensuring that raw materials used in battery production comply with international social and environmental standards.
4. **Extended Producer Responsibility:** The regulation enforces updated extended producer responsibility (EPR) measures starting August 18, 2025. Producers are responsible for financing the collection, treatment, and recycling of waste batteries, ensuring high recovery rates and minimizing environmental impacts. The updated targets include increased collection rates for portable batteries and enhanced recycling efficiencies for different battery chemistries. These measures are part of the EU's strategy to promote a circular economy, reduce waste, and increase the availability of secondary raw materials for new battery production.
5. **Material Recovery Rates:** To support the EU's circular economy objectives, the regulation sets specific targets for material recovery rates, effective from December 31, 2027. It mandates minimum recovery percentages for key raw materials, including cobalt, copper, lead, lithium, and nickel, from waste batteries. The targets are designed to maximize the recovery of valuable resources, reduce the need for primary raw material extraction, and minimize the environmental impact of battery waste. The regulation also requires regular reporting and auditing to ensure compliance and continuous improvement in recycling processes.
6. **Replaceability of Batteries:** From February 18, 2027, portable batteries must be designed for easy removal and replacement by end-users without requiring specialized tools. This requirement aims to enhance product longevity, reduce electronic waste, and facilitate the repair and maintenance of devices. By making batteries more accessible, the regulation supports the right to repair and aligns with the EU's sustainability objectives, encouraging consumers to replace batteries rather than discard entire products, thus extending the life of electronic devices and reducing waste.

3. Standards in SPINMATE

In SPINMATE project, standardisation activities play a pivotal role in ensuring that the developed solid-state battery (SSB) cells meet the stringent requirements of the electric vehicle (EV) industry. The project integrates a structured approach to define and implement standards, aligning with international best practices to guarantee quality, sustainability, and competitiveness. Key stakeholders, including **TME** as the EV sector end user, **AVESTA**, and **COMAU**, collaborated in WP2 to establish precise requirements for the 1 Ah and 10 Ah pouch SSB cells and their components. These requirements serve as critical inputs for subsequent work packages, including WP3 and WP6 for development, manufacturing, and scale-up, and WP5 for the optimisation of a 16 MWh/year proof-of-concept pilot line.

The SPINMATE project also emphasises sustainable and digitalised production processes, incorporating digital twins and machine learning to optimise manufacturing. An eco-design regulation ensures the disassembly of SSB cells with a focus on environmental and safety considerations. Standardisation within SPINMATE extends across four macro processes of cell manufacturing—cathode and anode electrode preparation, solid electrolyte membrane preparation, and cell assembly—ensuring that each step adheres to defined quality and safety standards. This comprehensive approach to standardisation not only enhances customer satisfaction by delivering customised solutions with reduced lead times but also strengthens the project's competitive positioning in the evolving EV market.

From D2.2, “Pilot line and eco-design regulation towards disassembly requirements” it is relevant to highlight the following statements.

“To facilitate dismantling as well as reuse and recycling of the components, the design of the battery pack should consider Standardize as much as possible the mechanical joints, to reduce the complexity of the needed tools and limit the flexibility requirements.”

“To enable efficient and safe handling of the battery pack, as well as maximise reuse and second life opportunities, the data connection interface should be standardised across the industry to allow a standardisation of the testing equipment used to evaluate SoH. This would simplify the testing procedures and facilitate the transition from one battery model to another.”

SPINMATE project underscores the critical importance of standardisation not only in the manufacturing processes of solid-state battery (SSB) cells but also in their design and end-of-life handling. By standardising mechanical joints, the complexity of tools required for dismantling is significantly reduced, simplifying disassembly processes and enhancing the potential for component reuse and recycling. Additionally, standardising data connection interfaces across the industry facilitates the use of uniform testing equipment for evaluating the SoH of battery packs. This approach enables efficient and safe handling, streamlines testing procedures, and maximises opportunities for reuse and second-life applications. These standardisation efforts align with the project's commitment to sustainability, safety, and competitiveness, paving the way for a seamless transition between battery models and fostering a circular economy in the EV industry.

4. Standardisation Methodology

As the Standardisation SubTask leader in the project, **INOVA** worked on the identification, interpretation and analysis of the relevant standards associable with the SPINMATE developments. Its implications on the developments and formats of the data, technology, devices, procedures, and interfaces were the subject of study, aiming at the widest possible market compliance and industry acceptance. The standardisation activities are represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Standardisation Activities roadmap in SPINMATE

A comprehensive background on standardisation was developed by gathering and analysing relevant literature, research outcomes, emerging trends, and dissemination materials from standardisation committees. This initial collection was then thoroughly discussed with the consortium to assess the importance and impact of specific standards on the development and application of SPINMATE technologies. The identified standards were evaluated and classified based on their relevance and potential or current adoption to ensure alignment and conformity with SPINMATE’s approaches.

In parallel with this research and analysis, SPINMATE actively collaborated with other projects and initiatives throughout its lifecycle, focusing on various topics, including standardisation. These discussions and the promotion of results emphasized the role of standardisation in Industry 4.0, with a particular focus on batteries and the EV sector.

The technological achievements of SPINMATE concerning standardisation are detailed at the end of the document. This includes a technology roadmap outlining how the project aligns with market and industry needs, along with future recommendations for standardisation bodies and committees.

INOVA, as part of Task 9.4 on standardisation activities, identified four key priorities for SPINMATE:

- Identify, monitor, and validate the standards through research and insights gained during the project.
- Analyse SPINMATE technology components to pinpoint key priorities for future standardisation actions.
- Enhance cooperation with other projects through workshops and dissemination activities, particularly with the SOLID4B cluster.

- Support the development of new regulations and standards to accelerate the adoption of advanced manufacturing systems.

To achieve these objectives, **INOVA** conducted extensive research and analysis of existing standards, ranging from general frameworks to those specifically addressing product quality control. The goal was to identify and categorise the most critical standards relevant to SPINMATE and the broader EV sector while determining which standards could be enhanced by the project's efforts, particularly within the context of the three use case scenarios.

The evaluation methodology adopted for this task is structured into two stages:

1. **State of the Art** – Assessing current standards and practices. The results of this stage are reported in this deliverable.
2. **Move Beyond** – Identifying opportunities for advancing standardisation, as illustrated in the figure below. The results of this stage will be reported in June 2026, for an updated version of this report.

Figure 2 - Standardisation evaluation methodology in SPINMATE

The **standardisation activities** in the SPINMATE project followed a structured two-stage approach to ensure alignment with existing standards and identify opportunities for advancement:

First Stage: State of the Art

The objectives of this stage were:

1. Conduct research on the current trends and gaps in standardisation analysing Batteries EU regulation.
2. Identify and classify key standards used by in SPINMATE.
3. Analyse the levels of application and importance of standards in SPINMATE.

4. Measure the anticipated benefits of implementing these standards.

Second Stage: Move Beyond

This stage will focus on:

1. Demonstrate the adoption of standards in SPINMATE standardisation use cases.
2. Investigating the complementarity between SPINMATE technologies and existing SoA standards.
3. Evaluation of SPINMATE's technological achievements to propose new standardisation elements for consideration by standardisation bodies and committees.

Implementation and Evaluation

Following this research, **INOVA** organised a task force with consortium partners to assess the application of standards within SPINMATE. This process involved identifying relevant standards and evaluating their importance based on ease and effectiveness of application. Partners rated the standards on a scale from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest) to establish a prioritised list of the most relevant standards for the project.

Workshop and Collaboration

To advance these efforts, **INOVA** presented the **Standardisation Methodology** during an online consortium meeting on **6th November 2024**. This workshop engaged all project partners, leveraging their diverse expertise and roles to brainstorm SPINMATE's compliance with existing standards, identify potential gaps, and explore how standards can address challenges and align with EU battery regulation priorities.

Tools and Outputs

To systematically collect data and insights, **INOVA**, in collaboration with **AVESTA**, developed the **Standardisation Assessment Survey**, detailed in the annex of this report. This tool facilitated the evaluation of SPINMATE's standardisation efforts, providing a foundation for aligning project activities with regulatory and industry needs.

Standards Evaluation

To support the representation of how standards are being applied in the different projects we used, in parallel ways, the creation and the re-evaluation of the Radar Chart. The Radar Chart is a graphical representation of relevant standards on the global radar screen – Figure 3.

Figure 3 - Radar Chart

The **Radar Chart** provides a simple view of the standardisation assessment, illustrating technology (or blips) all the elements that may be of relevance to project developments and highlighting the candidate standards for adoption and those standards that have been adopted as part of this joint effort.

This chart is divided into four quadrants, showing the SPINMATE strategy for delivery of the candidate standards - adoption, monitoring, or participation in development, or even in Ecosystem development of standards.

Each standard on the Radar Chart is used to provide visibility of the status and maturity of a standard or initiative. Each standard or initiative is first identified, and further continuously updated to track progress as the standard or initiative evolves. This continuous process of monitoring a standard or initiative includes the current action level (Adopted, Candidate, or Track), the quadrant and a link for a full description of the component standards.

SPINMATE Standardisation Assessment Survey

The evaluation questionnaire on Standardisation Activities in SPINMATE is divided into 3 parts:

- **PART I:** Identification, Categorisation and Importance Rating of Standards in SPINMATE.
- **PART II:** Assess standard practices in alignment with European Union goals for batteries and batteries waste.
- **PART III:** Description of Standardisation Use Cases – Best Practices examples of implementing standards to highlight its values, benefits and metrics.

5. Standardisation First Results – Part I

The following tables present the relevant standards identified by SPINMATE partners, in line with the project pilot line, identifying the specific standards, including how these are being categorized in terms of the level of applicability (Adopted, Candidate, or Track), and its level of importance (5 – High to 1 – Low) regarding respective use in SPINMATE activities.

5.1 Cell Assembly

Cathode Preparation

- **Wet Processing:** Includes medium-sized high-shear planetary mixing, coating, drying, and inline calendaring systems.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
IEC 63218 : Secondary cells and batteries containing alkaline or other non-acid electrolytes – Secondary lithium, nickel-cadmium and nickel-metal hydride cells and batteries for portable applications – Guidance on environmental aspects	Track	2	Provides requirements and recommendations on environmental aspects of secondary lithium, nickel-cadmium and nickel-metal hydride cells and batteries for portable applications (hereafter referred to as “relevant secondary cells and batteries”).
Sd1: Self-developed SOP and AVESTA internal standard	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of mixing, coating, drying, and inline calendaring systems for batteries is under development.
ISO9001 : Quality management systems — Requirements	Adopted	5	
ISO14001 : Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use	Candidate	5	
Sd2: Self-developed internal standard	Track	2	The systematic methodology of mixing, coating, drying a NMC811 cathode electrode.

- **Dry Processing:** Solid content mixing, granulation, homogenisation, extrusion, and calendaring, using specialised mixers and rollers.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
Sd3: Self-developed internal standard	Track	2	Systematic methodology of mixing components at high temperature and hot pressing resulting homogeneous mixtures. For preparation of dry-processed electrolyte membranes.

Anode Preparation

- Li-metal anode preparation involves thermal vapour deposition on a copper current collector with an artificial Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) layer.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1-Low; 2-Medium Low; 3-Medium; 4-Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information
Sd4: Self-developed SOP and AVESTA internal standard	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of lithium metal anode making using thermal vapour deposition on a copper current collector with an artificial Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) layer is under development.

Electrolyte Membrane Preparation

- Gel polymer solution is prepared with magnetic stirring, casting, and drying, utilising PET liners and PP separators, with plans for further upscaling.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
Sd5: Self-developed internal standard	Track	2	Systematic methodology of mixing, casting, and drying electrolyte membranes

10 Ah Cell Assembly

- Composed of electrode cutting, Z-fold stacking, welding, and pouch forming, the assembly includes modifications like protective layer removal for handling Li-metal and electrolyte membrane materials.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
IEC 62619 : Secondary cells and batteries containing alkaline or other non-acid electrolytes - Safety requirements for secondary lithium cells and batteries for use in industrial applications.	Track	3	Tests and requirements for the safe operation of secondary lithium cells and batteries used in industrial applications, including stationary applications. (except road vehicles).
Sd6: Self-developed SOP and AVESTA internal standard	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of electrode cutting, Z-fold stacking, welding, and pouch forming, including modifications like protective layer removal for handling Li-metal and electrolyte membrane materials, is under development.
Directive 2006/42/EC : Machinery directive	Adopted	5	
ISO 9001:2015 : Quality Management Systems	Adopted	5	
ISO 27001:2022 : Information Security Management	Adopted	5	
ISO 14001:2015 : Environmental Management Systems	Adopted	5	
ISO 45001:2018 : Occupational health and safety management systems	Adopted	5	
ISO 50001:2018 : Energy Management Systems	Adopted	5	

5.2 Separator Membrane Manufacturing

- Solid electrolyte membrane production is expected to use existing cathode equipment with adaptation for gel polymer preparation, liner casting, and PP separator integration. As the backup plan, the solid electrolyte membrane production will be produced at the

pre-pilot scale, processing and drying in batches before assembly to the standard 1 and 10 Ah pouch cell batteries.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
N/A			

- Further upscaling to roll-to-roll production may require additional modifications, deferred for later project stages.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
Sd7: Self-developed SOP and AVESTA internal standard	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of upscaling to roll-to-roll production is under development.

5.3 Sustainable SSB Cells, Modules, and Packs

Eco-Design and Disassembly

- The project emphasises design features that facilitate disassembly, reduce adhesive usage, and prioritise mechanical fastenings.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
Sd8: Self-developed SOP and SPINMATE proposed standard.	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of this section is initiated through Task 2.5 and crystallise to D2.2, and it is under development.
ISO 14040 : Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework	Adopted	5	
ISO 14044 : Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Requirements and guidelines	Adopted	5	
Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 : establishing a framework for the setting of eco-design requirements for sustainable products, amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and	Adopted	2	

Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and repealing Directive 2009/125/EC			
ISO 14051 - Environmental management — Material flow cost accounting — General framework	Adopted	5	

- Design considerations focus on using materials and assembly techniques (e.g., electricity-induced debonding) that allow efficient recycling and component recovery.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
Sd9: Self-developed SOP and SPINMATE proposed standard.	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of this section is initiated through Task 2.5 and crystallise to D2.2, and it is under development.

Guidelines for Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design

- A modular approach supports easy disassembly, with eco-design and automated dismantling processes to maximise reuse, recycling, and material recovery.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
Sd10: Self-developed SOP and SPINMATE proposed standard.	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of this section is initiated through Task 2.5 and crystallise to D2.2, and it is under development.

5.4 SPINMATE Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design

- **Pack Design:** Includes design for dismantling, with screws and bolts for easy disassembly and limited adhesives to enable recycling.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
ISO 12405-4:2018 : Electrically propelled road vehicles - Test specification for lithium-ion	Track	2	Specifies test procedures for the basic characteristics of performance, reliability and electrical functionality for the battery packs and systems for either high-power or high-energy applications.

traction battery packs and systems -Performance testing.			
ISO 19453-6:2020 : Road vehicles - Environmental conditions and testing for electrical and electronic equipment for the drive system of electric propulsion vehicles - Traction battery packs and systems.	Track	2	Specifies requirements for lithium-ion traction battery packs or systems used in battery electric, hybrid electric and fuel cell electric road vehicles. It describes the most relevant environmental stresses and specifies tests and test boundary conditions. This document establishes a classification of battery packs or systems and defines different stress levels for testing when a classification is applicable and required. The objective of this document is to specify standard test procedures and conditions to enable the observation of the reliability of the lithium-ion traction battery in the vehicle.
ISO 6469-1 Part 1 : Electrically propelled road vehicles - Safety specifications - Rechargeable energy storage system (RESS) - Amendment 1.	Track	2	Provides safety requirements for rechargeable energy storage systems.
Sd11: Self-developed SOP and SPINMATE proposed standard.	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of this section is initiated through Task 2.5 and crystalise to D2.2, and it is under development.

- **Module Design:** Designed for minimal adhesive use, modular assembly points for faster disassembly, and features for second-life adaptability.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information
Sd12: Self-developed SOP and SPINMATE	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of this section is initiated through Task 2.5 and crystalise to D2.2, and it is under development.

- **Cell Design:** Utilizes a solid polymer electrolyte with minimal solvent, ensuring safer and environmentally aligned production.

Identification of Standards	Applicability Level	Importance level	Additional Information

Sd13: Currently developed SOP from SPINMATE project combined with AVESTA internal standard.	Adopted	5	The systematic standard of cell design for dedicated SPINMATE SSE-based Li-metal battery pouch cells is developing during SPINMATE project running.
ISO9001 : Quality Management Systems - Requirements	Adopted	5	
ISO14001 : Environmental management systems — Requirements with guidance for use	Candidate	5	

Standards’ Applicability Level in SPINMATE

Most of the standards identified by the partners are being adopted in SPINMATE Pilot Line. Of the 32 standards identified, 22 (69%) are being adopted, 2 (6%) are considered candidates, while 8 (25%) are being Tracked.

Standards’ Importance Level in SPINMATE

Partners have rated the standards identified as important factor on SPINMATE Pilot Line activities, scoring an average of 4,1 from scoring of 1-5.

Self-developed Standards’ in SPINMATE

SPINMATE has identified 12 self-developed standards, where:

- 2 are Self-developed internal standard (2 on Cell Assembly, at Cathode Preparation and Membrane Preparation);
- 4 Self-developed SOP and **AVESTA** internal standard (1 on Cell Assembly - Cathode Preparation, 1 on Cell Assembly - Anode Preparation, 1 on Cell Assembly - 10 Ah Cell Assembly, and 1 on Separator Membrane Manufacturing);
- 1 Self-developed SOP and **AVESTA** internal standard (1 on SPINMATE Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design - Module Design);
- 4 Self-developed SOP and SPINMATE proposed standard (2 on Sustainable SSB Cells, Modules, and Packs - Eco-Design and Disassembly, 1 Sustainable SSB Cells, Modules, and Packs - Guidelines for Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design, and 1 on SPINMATE Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design - Pack Design).

SPINMATE Radar Chart presentation

Figure 4 is representing the standards identified by SPINMATE partners as the most relevant ones, according to the applicability level (from Track, to Candidate, and Adopted – from far to the

center of the radar), and using the “Colour code” to represent the importance level of the respective standard, from light blue for low importance to dark blue for high importance.

The illustration shows the greater level of importance of standards in SPINMATE, with a significant percentage of high important standards to the current practices within the project, as well a very interesting and promising number of standards (5) resulting from self-developed SOP and SPINMATE (standards Sd9, Sd10, Sd11, Sd12, and Sd13).

SPINMATE Radar Chart

Figure 4 - SPINMATE Radar Chart

6. Standardisation First Results – Part II

Within this second part of the standardisation assessment, it is analysed how SPINMATE is aligned with industry practices with the latest EU Battery Regulation, ensuring sustainability, safety, and efficiency throughout the battery lifecycle. Below is analysed how SPINMATE tackles – from standardisation point of view – carbon footprint reduction, responsible sourcing, and enhanced recycling, while also addressing performance, safety, and labelling standards. It will promote higher collection rates, second-life applications, and digital tracking through the battery passport. Additionally, this assessment includes key regulatory updates, including CE conformity, supply chain due diligence, extended producer responsibility, material recovery targets, and battery replaceability, ensuring compliance with EU sustainability goals.

6.1 Sustainability

SUSTAINABILITY: The regulation emphasises the need to reduce the carbon footprint of batteries throughout their lifecycle. It includes specific measures such as requiring the use of responsibly sourced raw materials, improving energy efficiency during production, and enhancing recycling capabilities to achieve circularity.

- [Manufacturing process of SPINMATE cells prioritise environmental impact reduction, particularly in the use of raw materials and energy efficiency.](#)

In the SPINMATE project, **AVESTA** always intend to use as low as possible the active materials content during electrode-making. In that case, the reason behind the rationalisation of cathode active materials amount reduction for the upscaling stage that **CERPOTECH** has proposed is supported by **AVESTA** and well aligned with EC. Moreover, **AVESTA** also always try to achieve energy efficiency, especially in the use of the dry room in the pilot line.

COMAU is committed to designing machinery characterized by high energy efficiency and reduced footprint. In SPINMATE, **COMAU** is responsible for the development of digital tools for process control and optimization. Those tools could be used for the traceability purposes needed for the implementation of the “battery passport”.

TUBS is investigating the solvent-free route to produce polymer solid-state battery cathodes. By this approach, the solvent that is used in conventional wet coating processes can be omitted. Additionally, the subsequent solvent drying step is not necessary anymore, reducing the energy consumption even further.

Since the activities performed at **CICe** are on a lab scale, the environmental impact is minimal. However, activities are planned to minimize usage of raw materials.

From **INEGI** point of view, the SPINMATE partners are currently focused on establishing a functional cell manufacturing process, which is being developed at the laboratory scale. After completing this stage successfully, efforts will shift towards optimizing the cell manufacturing system, with a particular emphasis on improving material and energy efficiency.

The cathode and cell preparation in **IREC** have not prioritized environmental impact reduction. Since these early activities are on a lab scale, we just focused on characterizing the cathode material in this step.

CERPOTECH uses renewable hydroelectric power for all their production processes when producing the cathode active material (CAM). While the current

pilot line for spray pyrolysis only enables the safe disposal of waste product from emission control filter due to cross contamination from previous production, in the case of a later scaled up production with production product line dedicated to the production of cathode active material, any product or precursor collected in emission control equipment could be recycled through the same process as for disassembled cells described in WP8.

- **Examples of sustainable standard practices in SPINMATE.**

Regarding energy efficiency, the previous trials in the **AVESTA** pilot line concluded that the dew-point range of -40 to -60 °C similarly prevents electrode contamination from the air in a dry room (oxygen/moisture/etc.). Especially when we pointed to the solid-state electrolyte configuration. So, for SPINMATE, **AVESTA** decided to use -40 °C as the minimum dew-point to keep the energy consumption low and improve energy efficiency. Furthermore, for the standard operational procedure, **AVESTA** always tries to minimise the scrap from the Li-metal anode production. It intends to use it as the direct feed for recycling activities.

Generally, cell assembly takes place in gloveboxes instead of dry rooms at **ISCF**, which was a strategic decision years ago due to the significant reduced energy consumption. The more difficult handling inside the boxes is compensated by a lots of semi automation and mechanical assisting parts and guides.

The development of a Digital Twin by **COMAU** will help to reduce scraps and to increase product quality.

TUBS as a university has no such strict standards as the industry. **TUBS** are investigating new materials and processes which needs a certain flexibility. Yet, the parameters for measurements are standardized as good as possible – e.g. the same cut-off voltages for cyclisation, the same frequency range for the impedance measurements etc.

The baseline performance currently refers to the SoA positive electrodes with catholyte (electrolyte contained within the cathode layer), as well as the previous solid-state cathodes developed at **CID** (internal background).

Under **CICe** knowledge, Material purchase is carried out with minimal required amounts, to minimize waste; The least possible amount of solvent in electrolyte processing is used; Samples are produced in the minimum required amount necessary to carry out characterization; Samples for partners are produced on demand; Samples are stored in inert conditions to minimize ageing; and Early electrochemical testing is carried out in small cells (coin cells), to minimize materials usage.

The SPINMATE partners are monitoring the environmental performance – under **INEGI** revision – of their activities through life cycle assessment in accordance with ISO 14040-44 standards. Potential improvement measures may be implemented after reaching the technical target KPIs.

Finally, from **CERPOTECH** vision, the spray pyrolysis process eliminates the need for hazardous organic solvents in CAM production.

6.2 Performance

PERFORMANCE: Although the directive focuses more on environmental aspects, it indirectly influences performance by setting standards for labelling and monitoring, ensuring that batteries meet minimum durability and efficiency levels, and contributing to overall sustainability.

- Performance assurance of SPINMATE cells (capacity, energy efficiency, State of Health (SoH) tracking).

In this stage, the SPINMATE cells are still not included in the **AVESTA** main activities in WP5 since the WP3 is still extending. However, for the initial trials as the validation procedure from WP3 (in **AVESTA**'s lab facility), the cell performance doesn't have any effect with the environmental aspect focuses.

ISCF mentions that, as this particular cell assembly is done very manually, there is no standard applicable. During testing, the mechanical pressure is monitored over the lifetime addition to the standard parameters, to evaluate the influence of the pressure to the performance.

For a university like **TUBS**, it is hard to ensure certain performances of the produced cells. Several steps of the SSB production processes are still done by hand (e.g. filling of the mixer/kneader or the insertion into the calendar as well as the cell assembly). Therefore, performances may vary more than in fully automated processes. To verify the performance of the produced cathodes, resistivity measurements are performed, and small coin-type cells are built and tested before assembling larger pouch cells. Additionally, **TUBS** is mainly focusing on cathode production, so the full cell performance also depends on the components delivered by other project partners.

TME, with support from other SPINMATE partners, defined protocols for testing 1 Ah and 10 Ah pouch cells to ensure that partners follow same protocols and thus ensure reliability of performance data. In the same deliverable targeted KPIs for capacity, and energy density are clearly stated together with method to calculate these KPIs. Calculations were also carried out with variable parameters to provide guidelines for required values to ensure targeted KPIs can be reached.

In this stage, the **CID** main activities in WP3 (coin cell validation) and WP7 (monolayer cell testing) did not focus on environmental aspects, but only on ensuring good electrochemical performance to achieve the targets of the project.

Activities in WP3, with **CICe** contributions, have been performed with focus on performance, capacity, cyclability, rate capability.

- Metrics used.

AVESTA: The baseline performance currently refers to the SoA Li-ion battery in liquid-state electrolyte performance, as well as the previous validated trials in the WP3 (lab scale). Or, if necessary, the engineering team always use the published high-impact paper journal results as the baseline to compare for SPINMATE cell trials.

ISCF: Standard physical values in comparison to well-known LIBs values.

TUBS: Areal weight / loading, Adhesive strength on the substrate, Electrical conductivity (cathodes), Full cell capacity (related to the theoretical capacity of the CAM), Cycle life / capacity retention.

TME: Method to calculate targeted KPIs were stated in D2.1 so that all partners use same methodology for calculating values.

CEA: Discharge capacity, Coloumbic efficiency, and Number of cycles before end of life.

CID: The baseline performance currently refers to the SoA solid-state batteries (SSBs) with polymer electrolytes, as well as the previous SSBs developed at CID (internal background).

CICe: Specific capacity, SOH.

6.3 Safety

SAFETY: The directive limits the use of hazardous substances like mercury and cadmium, directly impacting battery safety. It requires manufacturers to implement safety protocols in the production and disposal phases, ensuring safer handling and minimising risks during disassembly and recycling.

- [Safety protocols in place during the disassembly of cells and battery packs, and its application advantages.](#)

AVESTA: Currently, SPINMATE is not in the state of module/cell disassembly yet. The only expected advantage is the purity of the processed product after recycling because, with the disassembly process, we can separate and classify each battery component based on the precious material components before shredding and jumping to the further recycling process.

ISCF: only disassembles cells; Disassembly only of cells when very slow deep discharged to 0 V or if needed at least discharged to 3 V; Disassembly only in inert atmosphere. **ISCF** internal protocols.

TUBS: refer that small cells (coin-type) are disassembled in a glovebox by hand for post-mortem analysis. This is fine due to their low energy and working in a glovebox protects the scientists from hazardous materials. Multilayer cells with higher energies are usually deep discharged with low currents before opening them (in a glovebox) so the risk of critical failures or explosive events is minimized.

CEA: The safety of the cells is evaluated through abusive testing. Even if not enough to certify cells (as certification is only done on a final commercial cell by an accredited organism), the safety tests that are done in SPINMATE will contribute to confirm, as preliminary evaluation, that the technology will not bring highly problematic safety issues.

CICe: No cell is disassembled, except for specific characterization purposes. In that case, disassembly is carried out in an Ar-filled glovebox, with minimum exposure from the operator. The cells handled at CICe have low capacity (< 1 Ah)

- [Examples of safety standard practices in SPINMATE.](#)

AVESTA: In the initial design, to keep the safety of the recycling process, **AVESTA** already prepared the dedicated room and atmospheric maintained area for the recycling team activities in hangar-2 of the **AVESTA** HQ in Ninove. It planned to use a similar design to a dry room with a dedicated glove box for only the disassembly process.

ISCF: has its own internal protocols.

TUBS: When handling hazardous materials (e.g. the NMC active material), the responsible person is wearing protective masks (FFP-3 or fully ventilated masks with specific filters). Waste materials of these hazardous materials are disposed in specific containers so it cannot contaminate the environment.

CEA: example of abusive tests performed in SPINMATE include Nail penetration, Crush, Overcharge, External short-circuit, and Thermal runaway tests.

CICe: For coin cell disassembly: Disassemble the cells in a glovebox with the dedicated tweezers. Remove Li and store in a dedicated closed vessel inside the glovebox. Remove the other components and dispose separately in a closed vessel.

6.4 Collection

COLLECTION: The regulation establishes higher collection targets, specifying collection rates for different types of batteries, such as portable, industrial, and electric vehicle batteries. It also mandates the creation of accessible collection points and encourages producers to establish take-back schemes to ensure high recovery rates.

- [SPINMATE procedures established regarding collecting batteries at the end of life.](#)

AVESTA: All the EoL SPINMATE cells will be sent to the appointed partners to do the postmortem analysis, and the rest of the batteries will be directly sent to **AVESTA** for the recycling process in the WP8.

TUBS: Depending on the size (capacity) of the produced cells, **TUBS** is disposing them in special containers that are picked up by a waste disposal company. This also applies for cells that were opened for post-mortem analyses after cycling.

- [Cell disassembly procedures maximise the efficient use of materials.](#)

AVESTA: With the disassembly process, we can separate and classify each battery component based on the precious material components before shredding and jumping to the recycling process.

ISCF: Within this project, **ISCF** does only disassemble cells for material analytics reasons. An estimation of the impact to re-use of materials might be concluded by analytics of the complexity of component detachment.

TUBS: For small lab cells (coin-type or monolayer), cell recycling is not effective. But for larger cells or modules, it is necessary to have a dismantlable design to separate most of the components before further processing. This helps to increase the material purity during cycling compared to shredding whole modules.

6.5 Recycling and Second Life

RECYCLING AND SECOND LIFE: The regulation enforces specific recycling efficiency targets, such as mandatory recovery percentages for key materials like lithium, cobalt, and nickel. It also promotes the development of second-life applications, incentivising manufacturers to design batteries that can be easily repurposed or reused in different contexts. It supports the development of technologies that enable second-life applications, ensuring that valuable materials are recovered and reused efficiently.

- [Specific design elements that enable efficient recycling and second-life applications of SPINMATE batteries.](#)

AVESTA: The freestanding SPE used in the SPINMATE is designed to enable efficient recycling and second-life applications.

TME: In WP2, deliverable D2.2 provides guidelines for on the hazards and reversibility of different technologies for assembly at pack and module levels so that partners in charge of designing pack and module are aware of different options available.

- [Examples of standard practices for recycling and second life.](#)

AVESTA: It could be done either by effective separation of battery components before the recycling process or only replacing the EoL SPINMATE battery components (not only cells) with functional ones.

6.6 Content and Labelling

CONTENT AND LABELLING: To enhance transparency and safety, the regulation limits the use of harmful chemicals in batteries. It also mandates detailed labelling, including information about battery chemistry, capacity, carbon footprint, and materials used, ensuring that consumers and recyclers have the necessary data for proper handling and disposal. Manufacturers must reduce or eliminate harmful substances and ensure the battery content is clearly communicated for safe handling.

- [Hazardous materials minimised or avoided in SPINMATE cell components.](#)

AVESTA: It can be performed, but not optimally. Because the cathode material used in SPINMATE is NMC811, which still contains Co in it, as well as some organic solvents to prepare SPE and the NMP for cathode are classified as hazardous in some industrial fields.

ISCF: Standard liquid electrolytes from LiBs are replaced by polymer electrolytes.

TUBS: Especially in the automotive sector, high-capacity materials like NMC have to be used which are quite toxic. But in SPINMATE, **TUBS** is investigating the dry processing of SSB cathodes which avoids hazardous solvents in the production.

CICe: Hazardous materials are avoided or minimized as much as possible.

ARKEMA: Before optimizing the process, the first goal is to achieve the required performances. However, when developing a formulation, at similar performances, the less harmful chemical will be selected.

CERPOTECH: The SPINMATE consortium supported **CERPOTECH** for reducing the planned amount of CAM for the upscaling steps to a minimum to reduce the amount of nickel and cobalt used. SDS for the CAM is available and containers of CAM powder are labelled with danger pictograms and hazard statements.

- **Chemicals used and their safety measures.**

AVESTA: [n-methyl-2-pyrrolidinone-sds](#); [SDS KI-0059 LiFSI, Lithium bis\(fluorosulfonyl\)imide](#); [LiTFSI SDS](#); [LBG-00022e](#); [Lithium Bis\(oxalate\)borate 244761-29-3](#); etc.

All of the above-mentioned example chemicals are still used either in the lab scale trials or upscaling activities but keep it low as the battery fabrication standard.

ISCF: Standard liquid electrolytes from LiBs are replaced by polymer electrolytes. Lower flammability.

TUBS: NMC811: gloves, lab coat, filter masks and good ventilation in the labs.

CICe:

- Li (7439-93-2): H260, H314; P223, P231 + P232, P280, P305 + P351 + P338, P370 + P378, P422, EUH014
- PVDF-HFP (9011-17-0): Not a hazardous substance or mixture according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008
- EC (96-49-1): H302, H319, H373; P260, P264, P270, P301 + P312, P305 + P351 + P338, P314
- FEC (114435-02-8): H302, H315, H319, H317; P280, P301 + P312 + P330, P302 + P352, P305 + P351 + P338
- LiFSI (171611-11-3): H302, H313, H315, H318, H341; P201, P202, P260, P264, P270, P280, P301 + P330 + P331, P303 + P361 + P353, P304 + P340, P305 + P351 + P338, P310, P321, P363, P405, P501
- LiBOB (244761-29-3): H302, H317, H318; P261, P264, P280, P301 + P312, P302 + P352, P305 + P351 + P338
- LiNO₃ (7790-69-4): H272, H360; P220.
- MEK (78-93-3): H225, H319, H336; P210, P243, P280, P405, P501, EUH066.
- NMP (872-50-4): H315, H319, H335, H360D; P280, P302 + P352, P305+P351+P338, P308+P313
- C45 (1333-86-4): H351, P201, P202, P280, P308 + P313, P405, P501
- NMC811 (179802-95-0): H317, H334, H350, H372; P280, P302 + P352, P304 + P340, P314, P333 + P313.

CERPOTECH: Water soluble nickel and cobalt salts are hazardous chemicals and are handled as specified in the supplier's SDS. Any spill as well as cleaning water is disposed of through approved handlers of hazardous waste. The product, NMC 811 is also a hazardous material, especially in powder form, and is also handled according to SDS. Fume hoods, dust masks and gloves are used when handling NMC powders.

6.7 Communication

COMMUNICATION: The regulation introduces the concept of a "battery passport," a digital record containing essential information about each battery's composition, origin, and state of health (SoH). This standardisation facilitates interoperability, maintenance, and recycling efforts by providing consistent data across different battery models. This approach ensures efficient tracking and potential reuse of components.

- Battery pack design include standardised data interfaces to enable SoH evaluation across different models.

Battery pack design is out of the scope of the SPINMATE project.

- Simplification and enhancement of testing/reuse of components?

Even though battery pack design is out of the scope of the SPINMATE project, as the general explanation, the "battery passport" will enhance the testing/reuse of components inside the battery because all of the information regarding the materials, origin, shelf-life, expected EoL, etc. will appear in the integrated database.

6.8 Management

MANAGEMENT: The directive enforces producer responsibility, requiring management systems to oversee the entire battery lifecycle, from production to disposal. This includes automation and monitoring systems that align with sustainability targets, ensuring that batteries are efficiently managed and recycled. It encourages the use of digital platforms like PLCs (Programmable Logic Controllers), SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition), and HMI (Human-Machine Interface) systems to optimise efficiency and ensure compliance with EU environmental standards.

- Management systems (such as PLC, SCADA, HMI) are used to oversee battery manufacturing and disassembly processes? How are they applied?

AVESTA's roll-to-roll electrode coater is running based on the latest PLC technology, which is supported by the Industry 4.0 modular machine. In the case of the battery component's assembly for the 10 Ah pouch cell, it is backed with the integrated PLC and HMI systems. However, for the 1 Ah and smaller (monolayer) pouch cell, **AVESTA's** pilot line is adopting the semi-automatic system for cell assembly. Regarding the disassembly, it will be adopting the system from **COMAU** and some protocols explained in D2.2.

COMAU is providing guidelines for sensorised machineries to enable the quality control and traceability.

While all processes in CAM powder manufactured by spray pyrolysis can be fully or partially automated, **CERPOTECH's** pilot production line is currently only automated to a minor degree. Separate SCADA systems are in place for furnace control, but all other processes are currently manual.

- Systems optimisation for automation.

ABEE: Yes, in the SPINMATE cell assembly the machines are designed to use to support human work with some or whole part of automation.

CERPOTECH: The different CAM production processes are currently not optimised to be run with a common SCADA software, but all sensors and controllers could be integrated in a common control system with significant investment.

- [SPINMATE alignment with the Regulation on digital "battery passport" for transparency and lifecycle management, supported by digital tools for tracking.](#)

Through the activities in the SPINMATE WP8, **AVESTA** has a close collaboration for transparency and lifecycle management with **INEGI** and all related partners for the recycling and lifecycle analysis stuff. All the tracking data and required information will be carefully assessed and provided in the SPINMATE cells and module demonstrator by the end of the project.

In SPINMATE, **COMAU** is responsible for the development of digital tools for process control and optimization. Those tools could be used for the traceability purposes needed for the implementation of the "battery passport".

INEGI: SPINMATE partners are actively working to develop a functional battery cell while optimizing its performance, safety, and efficiency during the use phase. In alignment with the Regulation on the digital 'battery passport,' SPINMATE considers the entire lifecycle of the battery. After its long use in vehicles, when the battery pack no longer meets performance requirements for this application but remains functional, it is envisioned to be repurposed for secondary uses. If repurposing is not feasible, the battery will be directed towards disassembly and recycling, ensuring responsible resource management and fostering a circular economy."

CERPOTECH: The composition of the CAM is within the scope of a battery passport, so the passport would be of benefit for our raw material suppliers in introducing recycled materials in their refining processes.

6.9 New EU Battery Regulation updates

Requirement #	SPINMATE activities contributing to be compliant	Potential gaps which must be mitigated
1. CE Conformity Assessment	Regarding safety, performance, and environmental standards, currently, it will keep following each SPINMATE partner's internal standards.	The internal standards of each SPINMATE partner could possibly be different from the solid-state battery practical application needs since most of us are working with liquid-state cell manufacturing as the battery market's state-of-the art. The current market's solid-state battery manufacturing is only reaching the early stage of development.

<p>2. Battery Passport</p>	<p>All the tracking data and required information will be carefully assessed and provided in the SPINMATE cells and module demonstrator by the end of the project.</p>	<p>SPINMATE's output is only pouch cells and a module demonstrator; the pack demonstrator will be out of scope.</p>
<p>3. Supply Chain Due Diligence</p>	<p>Cooperation with European importers and manufacturers of raw materials, all of which aim to comply with regulations for sustainable and ethical production.</p>	<p>The major battery raw materials are not available enough inside the EU area.</p> <p>There will most likely not be enough scrapped batteries in the world to fulfill the recycled materials ratio goals set for European batteries for several decades due to the durability of the batteries.</p>
<p>4. Extended Producer Responsibility</p>	<p>Waste from CAM production could be easily introduced in the full-scale battery recycling process.</p>	<p>Further work would be needed to increase yield and minimize waste during production.</p>
<p>5. Material Recovery Rates</p>	<p><i>N/A at this point for SPINMATE.</i></p>	<p><i>N/A at this point for SPINMATE.</i></p>
<p>6. Replaceability of Batteries</p>	<p>SPINMATE project tries to approach this scope by the design of eco-design towards disassembly, which is part of the T2.5 activities and proposed in Deliverable 2.2.</p>	<p>SPINMATE's output is only pouch cells and a module demonstrator; the pack demonstrator will be out of scope.</p>

SPINMATE alignment with the new EU Battery Regulation Updates

SPINMATE effectively addresses the European Union's standardisation priorities for batteries through a comprehensive approach encompassing sustainability, performance, safety, collection, recycling and second life, content and labelling, communication, and management. Below are the key conclusions for each priority area:

- **Sustainability:** SPINMATE prioritises environmental impact reduction through responsible raw material sourcing, energy-efficient manufacturing, and recycling initiatives. Partners like **AVESTA** optimise material use and energy efficiency, while **CERPOTECH** employs renewable energy for cathode production. The project monitors environmental performance using life cycle assessments in alignment with ISO 14040-44, fostering a circular economy.
- **Performance:** To ensure consistent and reliable battery performance, SPINMATE employs standardised testing protocols, as outlined in WP2 deliverables. Metrics such as

capacity, energy efficiency, and State of Health (SoH) tracking are prioritised. Performance data is benchmarked against SoA batteries to validate the effectiveness of SPINMATE cells.

- **Safety:** The project integrates safety protocols throughout the production and disassembly processes. Measures include using inert environments for disassembly, protective handling of hazardous materials, and ensuring controlled conditions for recycling. Safety practices are tailored to minimise risks and enhance operational reliability.
- **Collection:** SPINMATE establishes clear procedures for collecting end-of-life batteries, directing them for post-mortem analysis or recycling. Efficient disassembly processes, such as component separation, increase material purity and recovery rates, supporting higher collection targets set by EU regulations.
- **Recycling and Second Life:** The project enables second-life applications and efficient recycling through innovative battery designs, such as freestanding solid polymer electrolytes (SPEs). Guidelines in WP2 address the hazards and reversibility of assembly technologies to optimise repurposing and recycling.
- **Content and Labelling:** SPINMATE reduces or avoids hazardous materials, favouring safer alternatives wherever possible. Labelling practices align with EU standards, ensuring transparency about battery composition, capacity, and environmental impact, critical for safe handling and recycling.
- **Communication:** Although battery pack design is outside SPINMATE's scope, the project supports the EU's "battery passport" initiative by developing digital tools for traceability and lifecycle management. These tools will enhance interoperability, maintenance, and recycling efforts by providing consistent and accessible data.
- **Management:** SPINMATE incorporates advanced management systems, such as PLC, SCADA, and HMI, to optimise manufacturing and disassembly processes. Digitalisation efforts by partners like **COMAU** enable real-time monitoring and process control, supporting lifecycle transparency and compliance with EU sustainability targets.

SPINMATE aligns with EU regulations by addressing key priorities through innovation, standardisation, and sustainability-focused practices. By integrating advanced tools and methodologies, the project contributes to the EU's goals of creating a sustainable and circular battery industry, enhancing transparency, safety, and efficiency throughout the battery lifecycle. Moreover, SPINMATE project is actively addressing several aspects of the updated EU Battery Regulation while identifying potential gaps that require mitigation to ensure compliance. For CE Conformity Assessment, SPINMATE currently adheres to internal safety, performance, and environmental standards set by each partner, but acknowledges that these may not fully align with the needs of practical solid-state battery applications, given the early stage of solid-state battery manufacturing. Regarding the Battery Passport, the project is compiling tracking data and essential information for its pouch cells and module demonstrator; however, the lack of a pack demonstrator remains a limitation. In Supply Chain Due Diligence, SPINMATE collaborates with European importers and manufacturers to comply with sustainable and ethical production regulations, though challenges persist in securing sufficient raw materials within the EU and meeting recycled materials ratios due to the durability of batteries. For Extended Producer Responsibility, SPINMATE integrates waste from CAM production into potential recycling processes, with additional efforts needed to minimise waste and increase production yields. While Material Recovery Rates are not yet addressed, SPINMATE contributes to Replaceability of Batteries by incorporating eco-design principles to facilitate disassembly. Despite these efforts, the absence of a pack demonstrator in the project scope highlights a recurring gap across several regulatory priorities, which will need to be addressed in future initiatives.

7. Standardisation First Results – Part III

On the last part of SPINMATE standardisation assessment is showcased the best practices in implementing standards through three key standardisation use cases, highlighting their value, benefits, and measurable impacts. These three Use Cases includes Adhesive Strength Measurement, Cathode Preparation by Wet Processing, and Life Cycle Assessment of Partners' Activities) – illustrating the role of standardisation in improving battery production efficiency, safety, and environmental performance within the SPINMATE project.

7.1 Use Case #1 – TUBS: Adhesive strength measurement

SPINMATE Standard: Adhesive strength measurement

In SPINMATE, **TUBS** partner applies adhesive strength measurements to evaluate the bonding quality of electrode coatings on substrate foils, ensuring consistency across various battery types, materials, and production processes. This standardised method involves controlling key parameters such as sample size, contact pressure, peel-off speed, and the surrounding atmosphere during each measurement, ensuring uniformity and comparability of results. The primary advantage of this approach is the elimination of operator influence, enhancing the reliability and reproducibility of the data. The metrics achieved are expressed in N/mm (MPa), providing quantitative and comparable adhesion results that are unaffected by external variables. This standardisation facilitates a robust assessment of electrode coatings, contributing to the optimisation of materials and processes in the development of solid-state batteries.

⁵ Haselrieder, W., et al. "Measuring the coating adhesion strength of electrodes for lithium-ion batteries." International Journal of Adhesion and Adhesives 60 (2015): 1-8.

7.2 Use Case #2 – CID: Cathode preparation by wet processing

SPINMATE Standard: Quality management systems — Requirements (ISO9001:2015)

In SPINMATE, **CID** partner demonstrates the application of ISO 9001: Quality Management System to ensure high-quality standards specifically in cathode preparation through wet processing. This standard is applied to critical stages of the process, including high-shear planetary mixing, coating, drying, and calendaring. By adhering to ISO 9001, **CID** implements good manufacturing practices (GMP) and ensures consistency and precision in cathode manufacturing. The key advantages of this approach include enhanced quality control, minimised variability, and improved process efficiency. Metrics achieved through this standard include maintaining active material loading within a deviation of <2% and achieving precise thickness and density control within ± 2 microns. These outcomes highlight **CID**'s commitment to producing high-performance cathode components while aligning with international quality standards.

7.3 Use Case #3 – INEGI: Life cycle assessment of partners activities

SPINMATE Standard: Environmental management — Life cycle assessment — Principles and framework (ISO 14040-44)

In SPINMATE, the **INEGI** partner applies ISO 14040:2006 principles for Environmental Management — Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate and reduce the environmental impacts of product design and manufacturing processes. This standard is implemented during the design or redesign of battery cells to identify opportunities for sustainability improvements. Key advantages include the identification of environmental hotspots, allowing targeted actions to mitigate impacts, and informed decision-making based on comprehensive data about environmental performance. Additionally, applying this standard enhances the project's brand reputation by showcasing a commitment to sustainability and strengthens stakeholder trust and customer loyalty. Cost savings are another benefit, as resource and energy efficiency initiatives help lower operational expenses. While specific metrics are dependent on the final cell design and developed processes, ISO 14040:2006 provides a robust framework for achieving environmental goals within SPINMATE.

8. Conclusions

The preliminary results of SPINMATE's standardisation activities underscore the project's significant alignment with international and EU standards, demonstrating its commitment to quality, sustainability, and innovation in SSB development. Among the 32 standards identified, 69% have been adopted, 25% are being tracked, and 6% are considered candidates for future implementation. Partners rated these standards as crucial to pilot line activities, with an average importance score of 4.1 out of 5. Additionally, SPINMATE has developed 12 self-defined standards tailored to critical processes, including cell assembly, cathode and anode preparation, and eco-design principles, reflecting the project's proactive approach to addressing industry needs. The SPINMATE Radar Chart highlights the relevance and maturity of these standards, with a promising number resulting from self-developed initiatives. The project also aligns closely with updated EU Battery Regulation priorities, addressing sustainability, performance, safety, and recycling requirements while advancing innovative practices like eco-design for battery disassembly and second-life applications. Notably, SPINMATE's methodologies, such as life cycle assessments and standardised quality protocols, have been applied effectively in its use cases, including adhesive strength measurement, cathode preparation, and environmental impact evaluation, showcasing the tangible benefits of standardisation. Despite these advancements, the project identifies gaps, such as the absence of a pack demonstrator, which present opportunities for future initiatives to further enhance compliance and innovation in the evolving EV sector.

The preliminary results on standardisation described in this report will be promoted as part of the SPINMATE project's dissemination activities. SPINMATE will boost awareness of standardisation topics by actively engaging with standardisation committees, collaborating with initiatives like SOLID4B, and leveraging dissemination activities to share its findings and methodologies. The use of tools such as the Radar Chart and the Standardisation Assessment Survey provides a structured approach to evaluating and communicating the importance and applicability of standards. Furthermore, the project's focus on developing self-defined standards tailored to cutting-edge battery technologies showcases the innovative potential of standardisation, setting an example for the broader industry. By demonstrating the tangible benefits of applying and advancing standards, SPINMATE not only enhances its market competitiveness but also encourages industry-wide adoption of standardisation practices, contributing to the development of a sustainable and regulated EV battery market.

In parallel with the testing and validation of the SPINMATE pilot line, the standards will be re-evaluated to identify current regulatory needs and research findings that could lead to innovative approaches in battery manufacturing processes. The final results of Standardisation activities in SPINMATE will be included in D9.7, in June 2026.

ANNEX 1 – Standardisation Survey

1. PART 1 For each SPINMATE Pilot Line Manufacturing Process:

A. Identify standardised activities, methods, and practices implemented in each.

B. Categorise each into the adoption levels: T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted.

C. Rate on a scale of 1 to 5 (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High), how important?

1.1 Cell Assembly

1.1.1 Cathode Preparation:

- **Wet Processing:** Includes medium-sized high-shear planetary mixing, coating, drying, and inline calendaring systems.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

- **Dry Processing:** Solid content mixing, granulation, homogenisation, extrusion, and calendaring, using specialised mixers and rollers.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

1.1.2 Anode Preparation:

- Li-metal anode preparation involves thermal vapour deposition on a copper current collector with an artificial Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) layer.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

1.1.3 Electrolyte Membrane Preparation:

- Gel polymer solution is prepared with magnetic stirring, casting, and drying, utilising PET liners and PP separators, with plans for further upscaling.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

--	--	--	--

1.1.4 10 Ah Cell Assembly:

- Composed of electrode cutting, Z-fold stacking, welding, and pouch forming, the assembly includes modifications like protective layer removal for handling Li-metal and electrolyte membrane materials.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

1.2 Separator Membrane Manufacturing

- Solid electrolyte membrane production is expected to use existing cathode equipment with adaptation for gel polymer preparation, liner casting, and PP separator integration. As the backup plan, the solid electrolyte membrane production will be produced at the pre-pilot scale, processing and drying in batches before assembly to the standard 1 and 10 Ah pouch cell batteries.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

- Further upscaling to roll-to-roll production may require additional modifications, deferred for later project stages.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

1.3 Sustainable SSB Cells, Modules, and Packs

Eco-Design and Disassembly:

- The project emphasises design features that facilitate disassembly, reduce adhesive usage, and prioritise mechanical fastenings.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

--	--	--	--

- Design considerations focus on using materials and assembly techniques (e.g., electricity-induced debonding) that allow efficient recycling and component recovery.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

Guidelines for Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design:

- A modular approach supports easy disassembly, with eco-design and automated dismantling processes to maximise reuse, recycling, and material recovery.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

1.4 SPINMATE Battery Pack, Module, and Cell Design

- **Pack Design:** Includes design for dismantling, with screws and bolts for easy disassembly and limited adhesives to enable recycling.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

- **Module Design:** Designed for minimal adhesive use, modular assembly points for faster disassembly, and features for second-life adaptability.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

- **Cell Design:** Utilizes a solid polymer electrolyte with minimal solvent, ensuring safer and environmentally aligned production.

Identification of Standards	Categorisation (T: Track; C: Candidate, A: Adopted)	Importance Rate (1- Low; 2- Medium Low; 3- Medium; 4- Medium High; 5 - High)	Additional Information

PART 2: Assess SPINMATE activities to align with EC priorities

As described in EU Directive 2006/66/EC (and replaced with the new EU Battery Regulation (Regulation 2023/1542), which came into force on August 17, 2023.

1. **SUSTAINABILITY:** The regulation emphasises the need to reduce the carbon footprint of batteries throughout their lifecycle. It includes specific measures such as requiring the use of responsibly sourced raw materials, improving energy efficiency during production, and enhancing recycling capabilities to achieve circularity.

- a. How does the manufacturing process of SPINMATE cells prioritise environmental impact reduction, particularly in the use of raw materials and energy efficiency?

- b. Provide specific examples of sustainable standard practices in SPINMATE.

2. **PERFORMANCE:** Although the directive focuses more on environmental aspects, it indirectly influences performance by setting standards for labelling and monitoring, ensuring that batteries meet minimum durability and efficiency levels, and contributing to overall sustainability.

- a. How does the project ensure the performance of SPINMATE cells (capacity, energy efficiency, State of Health (SoH) tracking)?

- b. Which metrics are used?

3. **SAFETY:** The directive limits the use of hazardous substances like mercury and cadmium, directly impacting battery safety. It requires manufacturers to implement safety protocols in the production and disposal phases, ensuring safer handling and minimising risks during disassembly and recycling.

a. Which safety protocols are in place during the disassembly of cells and battery packs? Briefly explain their application advantages.

b. Provide specific examples of safety standard practices in SPINMATE.

4. **COLLECTION:** The regulation establishes higher collection targets, specifying collection rates for different types of batteries, such as portable, industrial, and electric vehicle batteries. It also mandates the creation of accessible collection points and encourages producers to establish take-back schemes to ensure high recovery rates.

a. Which procedures in SPINMATE are established regarding collecting batteries at the end of life?

b. How do cell disassembly procedures maximise the efficient use of materials?

5. **RECYCLING AND SECOND LIFE:** The regulation enforces specific recycling efficiency targets, such as mandatory recovery percentages for key materials like lithium, cobalt, and nickel. It also promotes the development of second-life applications, incentivising manufacturers to design batteries that can be easily repurposed or reused in different contexts. It supports the development of technologies that enable second-life applications, ensuring that valuable materials are recovered and reused efficiently.

a. Are there specific design elements that enable efficient recycling and second-life applications of SPINMATE batteries?

b. Provide examples of standard practices for recycling and second life.

6. **CONTENT AND LABELLING:** To enhance transparency and safety, the regulation limits the use of harmful chemicals in batteries. It also mandates detailed labelling, including information about battery chemistry, capacity, carbon footprint, and materials used, ensuring that consumers and recyclers have the necessary data for proper handling and disposal. Manufacturers must reduce or eliminate harmful substances and ensure the battery content is clearly communicated for safe handling.

a. Are hazardous materials minimised or avoided in SPINMATE cell components? Justify.

b. Specify any chemicals used and their safety measures.

7. **COMMUNICATION:** The regulation introduces the concept of a "battery passport," a digital record containing essential information about each battery's composition, origin, and state of health (SoH). This standardisation facilitates interoperability, maintenance, and recycling efforts by providing consistent data across different battery models. This approach ensures efficient tracking and potential reuse of components.

a. Does the battery pack design include standardised data interfaces to enable SoH evaluation across different models?

b. How does this simplify and enhance the testing/reuse of components?

8. **MANAGEMENT:** The directive enforces producer responsibility, requiring management systems to oversee the entire battery lifecycle, from production to disposal. This includes automation and monitoring systems that align with sustainability targets, ensuring that batteries are efficiently managed and recycled. It encourages the use of digital platforms like PLCs (Programmable Logic Controllers), SCADA (Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition), and HMI (Human-Machine Interface) systems to optimise efficiency and ensure compliance with EU environmental standards.

a. What management systems (such as PLC, SCADA, HMI) are used to oversee battery manufacturing and disassembly processes? How are they applied?

b. Are these systems optimised for automation? Justify.

c. How is SPINMATE aligned with the Regulation on digital "battery passport" for transparency and lifecycle management, supported by digital tools for tracking (responsible sourcing, efficient use, and repurposing to foster a circular economy.)? Justify.

From the following key updates from **EU Directive 2006/66/EC to the new EU Battery Regulation (Regulation 2023/1542)**, which activities in SPINMATE you are implementing are aligned with such battery's requirements for Europe and/or which are the potential gaps, i.e., what should be taken into consideration in the future actions to comply with such requirement (regarding your role in SPINMATE).

Requirement #	SPINMATE activities contributing to be compliant	Potential gaps which must be mitigated
1. <i>CE Conformity Assessment</i>		
2. <i>Battery Passport</i>		
3. <i>Supply Chain Due Diligence</i>		
4. <i>Extended Producer Responsibility</i>		
5. <i>Material Recovery Rates</i>		
6. <i>Replaceability of Batteries</i>		

PART 3 – USE CASE [open for all technical partners]

Describe a **USE CASE example** of implementing one or more standards mentioned above, highlighting the advantages of using such standardised practice/method/equipment in SPINMATE and presenting the **metrics** achieved.

Use Case - <TITLE>:

Standard	
How it is applied (in which conditions/ which operations this standard is applied for)	
Key advantages of applying this standard	
Metrics achieved (specific results achieved by applying such standard)	